

Novel Mixed-ligand Derivatives of Bis(acetoacetanilido)-, Bis(*o*-acetoacetanisidido)- and Bis(*o*-acetoacetotoluidido)nickel(II) with some Biologically Active 5-Pyrazolones

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5-Pyrazolones possess various biological activities¹. The substituted pyrazolones act as monodentate, bidentate and sometimes tridentate ligands towards transition and inner-transition metals². They have been gaining increasing importance as chelating agents for extraction of metals³. There has been continuing interest in the synthesis of some metal chelates of acetoacetanilides^{4,5}. Although mixed-ligand derivatives of nickel(II)- β -diketonate and β -diketoesters with some potentially bi- and tridentate heterocyclic nitrogen donors⁶ and potentially mono-, bi- and tridentate 5-pyrazolone derivatives⁷, have been described, but no report was found on analogous derivatives of bis(acetoacetanilido)-, bis(*o*-acetoacetanisidido)- and bis(*o*-acetoacetotoluidido)nickel(II) with 5-pyrazolones. Hence, we have examined the ligational behaviour of 5-pyrazolone derivatives, viz. 3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (MP) and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (MPHP) with bis(acetoacetanilido)-, bis(acetoacetanisidido)- and bis(acetoacetotoluidido)nickel(II).

MP

MPHP

Results and Discussion

The formation of nickel(II) mixed-ligand complexes may be represented as

where, (L-L) H = acetoacetanilide (aaaH), *o*-acetoacetanisidide (aaansH) or *o*-acetoacetotoluidide (aatdH), and L = 3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (MP) or 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (MPHP). The resulting derivatives are non-

hygroscopic coloured solids (Table 1). All are soluble in DMF and partially soluble in alcohol and dioxane.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Ni% : Found/ (Calcd.)
[Ni(aaa) ₂ (MP) ₂]	Grey	280	9.09 (9.67)
[Ni(aaa) ₂ (MPHP) ₂]	Grey	300	7.98 (7.73)
[Ni(aaans) ₂ (MP) ₂]	Grey	260	9.02 (8.80)
[Ni(aaans) ₂ (MPHP) ₂]	Grey	270	7.75 (7.16)
[Ni(aatd) ₂ (MP) ₂]	Grey	270	9.79 (9.24)
[Ni(aatd) ₂ (MPHP) ₂]	Grey	240	7.02 (7.46)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Unlike parent compounds, the adducts do not show an infrared bands at 3550–3400 cm⁻¹ and hence they are anhydrous. The two significant bands for acetoacetanilide, *o*-acetoacetanisidide or *o*-acetoacetotoluidide and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ (acetylcarbonyl) and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ (amide carbonyl) have been observed at 1540–1550 and 1590–1605 cm⁻¹ regions^{4,6} respectively, in all the adducts.

Both the ligands, MP and MPHP possess three potential donor sites : (i) and (ii) the ring nitrogens 1 and 2 and (iii) the cyclic carbonyl oxygen. The possibility of ring nitrogen 1 coordination to nickel(II) is ruled out by the zwitterion mechanism⁸. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band of MP and MPHP (~1585 cm⁻¹) remains almost unchanged and merged with $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ (amide carbonyl) in the complexes, suggesting that the ring nitrogen 2 is not involved in coordination. A comparison of the ir bands of the free 5-pyrazolones and their complexes show that the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ bands observed at 1620 and 1610 cm⁻¹ in the uncoordinated MP and MPHP respectively, shifted to lower wavenumbers⁹ (1560–1570 cm⁻¹) in all the complexes. This indicates the bonding of the cyclic carbonyl oxygen of these 5-pyrazolones to nickel(II).

The observed magnetic moments of these mixed-ligand complexes (3.05–3.17 B.M.) are consistent with octahedral nickel(II)¹⁰ complexes. Their molar conductances (12.8–15.5 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) in 10⁻³ M DMF solutions suggest that they are non-electrolytic in nature¹¹.

The electronic spectrum of one of the compounds, $[\text{Ni}(\text{aadt})_2(\text{MPHP})_2]$ exhibits three bands at 285, 430 and 658 nm. The first intense uv band ($\epsilon = 2437$) is comparable to a band observed for octahedral bis-adducts of the metal acetylacetonates¹². The remaining two bands at 430 and 658 nm are most probably due to $d-d$ transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$ respectively. The positions and assignments of these bands suggest octahedral environment around the nickel(II) ion¹³ in the adduct.

The analytical data and all the above studies suggest that the adducts may be formulated as $[\text{Ni}(\text{L-L})_2(\text{L})_2]$, where (L-L) H = aaaH, aaansH or aatdH and L = MP or MPHP. Considering the established *trans*-octahedral structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{py})_2]$ (where acacH = acetylacetonone and py = pyridine) by crystal structure determinations¹⁴, it is reasonable to propose an octahedral structure of the present mixed-ligand complexes where the ligands, L span *trans* vertices.

Experimental

3-Methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (Wilson), $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Polypharm), ethyl acetoacetate (B.D.H.), hydrazine hydrate (Sisco-Chem.) and acetoacetanilide, *o*-acetoacetanilide and *o*-acetoacetotoluidide (Aldrich) were used as supplied. 3-Methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one was prepared by the reported method¹⁵. The parent compounds $[\text{Ni}(\text{aaa})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{aaans})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{aadt})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ were prepared by the reported methods⁷.

Mixed-ligand complexes. General procedure : A stoichiometric quantity of MP or MPHP (0.02 mol) dissolved in an excess of ethanol (~30 ml) was added to a solution of the appropriate parent compound (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (~40 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 7–8 h at 80°. The resulting coloured crystals were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure (yields 52–56%).

C, H and N were determined microanalytically. Ni was estimated as nickel dimethylglyoximate¹⁶. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant. Ir spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1620 FT-IR spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMF) on a Shimadzu UV 160 spectrophotometer. Molar conductance was measured in DMF on a Toshniwal CL 01.02A conductivity bridge.

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